

Design of an Ammonia-fed Nuclear Thermal Propulsion System for Reusable Space-tug in Cislunar Orbits

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Since the first nuclear propulsion projects in the 50s-70s, nuclear thermal propulsion has been considered the technology suitable to assert human presence in a cislunar environment by using tugs and shuttles operating between the Earth and future lunar stations; nowadays, most of the space agencies have revived interest in building a human outpost on the Moon and an orbital station between the Earth and the Moon. A space tug operating between these stations will be a necessary technology in the next decades. This work demonstrates that a space tug using a nuclear thermal propulsion system fed by ammonia is the optimal solution to cover this role; such a system, thanks to the ISRU of the ammonia present on the Moon and a propellant management system based on autogenous pressurization, allows to perform multiple roundtrips between the Moon and the Lunar Gateway having as the only limit to its operational life the burnup of the nuclear fuel. Using a single fluid inside the propulsion system is the main feature of this system that allows it to be completely reusable and to reduce the mass to be launched at the beginning of the mission into Earth orbit compared to other propulsion systems using pressure-fed solutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The space missions that will characterize the next decades, according to most of the world's space agencies¹ will be commercial missions between Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and Geosynchronous Equatorial Orbit (GEO), commercial and crewed missions in the cis-lunar environment, and crewed missions to Mars. Nuclear propulsion is considered the enabling technology to bring the mankind to Mars; the increase in the specific impulse given by hydrogen-fed nuclear thermal propulsion (NTP) systems allows to complete a mission to Mars in much shorter times compared to chemical propulsion systems, placing astronauts at a lower risk related to excessive exposure to cosmic radiation². In DRA 5.0³ the thermo-nuclear engine (and in particular the model given by the "Pewee" engine⁴) was selected as the baseline for the Martian mission thanks to its overwhelming performances (high thrust, high specific impulse, low initial mass in LEO (IMLEO), and high tolerance to payload mass growth) and the great legacy left by the Rover/NERVA project; this project has successfully tested on the ground several NTP

engines (including the "Pewee") at the performance levels required for a human mission to Mars⁵. During the Rover/NERVA project, one of the first ideas was to use nuclear propulsion for the last stage of a Saturn V rocket to achieve a crewed mission to the Moon; however, this idea was abandoned following the first failed tests of the Kiwi-B⁶. One year after the Apollo 11 mission, Wernher von Braun proposed the NASA Integrated Space Program Plan (1970 to 1990). The main part of the plan was the development of a space shuttle, an orbiting space station, and a reusable NTP propulsion stage delivering cargo and crew to the Moon for the construction of a lunar base, and then for a human landing on Mars⁷. To date, while nuclear propulsion dominates future crewed interplanetary mission scenarios, it does not seem to be the technology to focus on for commercial missions in the cislunar environment^{1,8} where chemical propulsion systems still seem to be the best solution; interest in using nuclear propulsion for missions to the Moon appears to have died down. However, some works in the literature demonstrate how NTP could be a valid alternative for the cislunar environment. Reynolds et al.⁹ studied the possibility of using an NTP system-propelled space tug (consisting of a stage of the architecture studied for the mission to Mars) to move tons of payload in the cislunar space (High Earth Orbit - HEO, Near Rectilinear Halo Orbit - NRHO and LLO) and compared the performance of the system with the ones given by a chemical propulsion system: the NTP space-tug showed a payload capability that was at least twice the one of the chemical tug for several analyzed transfer orbits. Harnack et al.¹⁰ compare the payload capabilities of a hydrogen-fed NTP space tug with one of a chemical propulsion system space vehicle for a round-trip mission between Nuclear Safe Orbit (NSO) and Low Lunar Orbit (LLO). The authors determined again the benefit of using the NTP systems to increase the payload capability of the spacecraft while pointing out that the comparison is greatly dependent on the selected launcher for the mission i.e. the IMNSO considered. While in previous works, the authors consider missions to the Moon requiring one or two launches to insert the propulsion system into orbit, Borowski et al.⁷ consider a cargo mission between LEO and the Moon with a reusable space-tug employing three launches for in-orbit assembly. The system they proposed uses hydrogen as a propellant distributed in two tanks, and

the initial mass in NSO (IMNSO) is 186.7 t, demonstrating that the NTP is a suitable system to move large masses of payload in a cislunar environment. The space tug proposed by Borowski et al.⁷ is also reusable, and the authors propose refilling the propellant by launching the tanks into Earth orbit. The authors also demonstrate the use of an NTP system for crewed missions to the Moon and one-week missions for space tourism between the Earth and the Moon highlighting how the NTP could play a crucial role for cargo missions and human exploration towards our natural satellite. The studies cited above demonstrate how a shuttle propelled by the NTP is very versatile in the cislunar environment, being able to cover the entire spectrum of missions of interest in that region. However, most NTP systems presented in the literature for missions in cislunar environments assume to use hydrogen as a propellant and do not consider alternative propellants^{11,12}. Harnack et al.¹⁰ discuss the possibility of using ammonia for the NTP in the roundtrip mission between NSO and LLO, however, they highlight how such solution is inferior in terms of payload capabilities to a space-tug using a chemical propulsion system and estimates that the system would not even be able to have enough propellant to return to NSO if inserted into orbit with a single launch. These observations are true if there is not yet a propellant mining outpost on the Moon⁸ or if the possibility of a propellant refill in lunar orbit is not considered. Propellant refilling in lunar orbit for future space missions is indicated by various authors, both for multiple roundtrips between Earth and Moon⁷ and for trips between LLO and NRHO⁹ and for missions from Moon to Mars¹¹. Although various authors^{7,9,13} suggest the use of hydrogen as a propellant for reusable space-tug, this propellant presents some non-negligible criticalities such as the need to be stored in cryogenic conditions, the low density and the difficulty of its mining/production on the Moon soil. Kornuta et al.⁸ report a detailed analysis of the commercial aspects of hydrogen/oxygen propellant production on the moon. From this analysis, it is easy to estimate the high costs and complexity of hydrogen production and storage compared to other propellants, such as ammonia, which does not need to be stored in cryogenic conditions and can be found directly inside the lunar regolith (even if in lower quantities than water; the concentration relative to water is 6.03%⁸). From the perspective of a reusable space-tug, the advantage of using NTP compared to classic chemical propulsion systems does not lie so much in being able to maximize the payload capabilities, since this aspect loses importance thanks to multiple roundtrips between the target orbits, but in the possibility of being able to use a single propellant to obtain high performance and increase the operational life of the vehicle. In these terms, ammonia can be a better alternative to hydrogen thanks to the reduction in costs and complexity not only for the spacecraft but also for the infrastructures dedicated to the production of propellants on the lunar surface. Nikitaeva and Thomas¹¹ demonstrated how In-Situ

Resources Utilization (ISRU) can enable ammonia to be the selection propellant for reusable spacecraft missions between the Moon and Mars. In this paper, the idea of a reusable space tug using an ammonia-fed NTP system to move tons of payloads in multiple roundtrips in the cislunar environment is presented.

II. MISSION SCENARIO

The mission scenario analyzed in this work, from which to draw the requirements for the sizing of the NTP system for the reusable space-tug, foresees the departure of the system from a Nuclear Safe Orbit (NSO), assumed at 1000 km¹⁴. The system is supposed to be inserted into orbit by a single launcher with a fairing capacity of about 30 metric tons to exploit the advantages of the compactness of the configuration given by using ammonia and avoiding an assembly of the system in Earth orbit. Once in NSO, the system will perform a first maneuver at 3288 m/s to enter an LTI trajectory. Once LLO is reached, another firing at 900 m/s will allow the system to circularize the orbit around the Moon; in this orbit, the system will do the first refilling of the tank and then perform multiple roundtrips between LLO and NRHO (orbit of the Lunar Gateway). According to Reynolds et al.⁹, the total Δv for one roundtrip is 1404 m/s, and typical values of transportable payloads are 16 metric tons for the trip to NRHO and 3 metric tons for the trip to LLO. The space tug will reload the propellant after a series of multiple roundtrips and will continue to transport payloads between the two stations. Once the limit of performable missions is reached, which can be dictated either by safety requirements, the durability of the propellant management system, or the burnup of the nuclear fuel, the system will end its life either returning to NSO or going into an ultra-high orbit¹³. Table I reports the information related to each firing of the propulsion system, while Fig. 1 reports a bat chart of the proposed mission scenario.

Fig. 1. Mission Scenario Bat Chart

Table I. Mission Maneuvers and Transfer Times

Maneuver	Δv (m/s)	Transfer Time (days)
TLI	3288	3
Moon circularization (LLO)	900	0
LLO-NRHO roundtrip	1404	0.5 and 0.5

II. PROPULSION SYSTEM DESIGN

Once the mission requirements in terms of IMNSO and Δv from Earth orbit have been established, the preliminary sizing of the space tug components can be performed. The reactor's pressure vessel (Eq.(4)), the shadow shield layers (Eq.(1)-(2)), and the turbopump assembly (Eq.(3)) masses are estimated based on the designed nuclear reactor and semi-empirical formulas present in the literature^{15,16} and reported below:

$$m_y = \frac{\rho_y \pi}{3} [t_1(r_1^2 + r_1 r_2 + r_2^2) + t_3(r_3^2 + r_3 r_4 + r_4^2)] \quad (1)$$

$$m_n = \frac{\rho_n \pi}{3} [t_2(r_2^2 + r_3 r_2 + r_3^2) + t_4(r_4^2 + r_5 r_4 + r_5^2)] \quad (2)$$

$$m_{tp} = 48(P_{tp} e^{-6})^{0.53} \quad (3)$$

$$m_{pv} = \frac{15\pi(r_{pv}^3)p_c\rho_{pv}}{\sigma_{pv}} \quad (4)$$

The r and t parameters present in Eq.(1)-(2) represent the shadow shield's layers thicknesses and radius, as reported in Fig. 2. They can be estimated by following an iterative procedure and by knowing the reactor's power level and envelope, and the desire radiation dose at the payload plane, as described in the work from Marshall¹⁵.

Fig. 2. Shadow Shield Layers Parameters¹⁵

The nozzle mass has not been included among the components since the proposed system will use nozzles integrated into the individual coolant channels of the nuclear reactor; this allows for a reduction in the total size of the system by about two meters, maintaining the same

level of performance^{17,18} and is in line with the design driver of the ammonia NTP to minimize the envelope of the propulsion system.

II.A. Nuclear Reactor

The nuclear reactor proposed for this mission is a HALEU particle bed reactor whose top view is shown in Fig. 3. A previous work¹⁹ reports the methodology followed for the design of this reactor; what is important to underline is that the coolant channels of the proposed configuration are filled with fuel particles so that the flow crosses the particle bed axially and then expands through the integrated nozzle, as shown in Fig. 4. The axial crossing was inserted to enhance the decomposition of the ammonia flow, enhanced also by inserting a catalytic bed in the first 20 cm of the channel. The decomposition of ammonia would cause an increase in the specific impulse of about 40%; however, in this work, it was assumed that ammonia does not decompose, and the only effect of the proposed configuration is to introduce a pressure loss of almost 20 bar inside the channels, to size the propulsion system in a sort of worst-case scenario. A multiphysics analysis conducted using OpenMC and a simplified 1.5D thermo-hydraulic model (more details are described in Puccinelli et al.¹⁹) provided the results reported in Table II for the reactor design and propellant properties.

Fig. 3. HALEU Particle Bed Reactor Top View

Fig. 4. Reactor's Coolant Channels Filled with Fuel Particles

Table II. Propulsion System Features

Parameter	Value
Core Diameter (m)	1.10
Reactor Diameter (m)	1.60
Reactor Length (m)	0.9
k_{eff} @ BOL	1.05722 +/- 0.00065
Control drums worth (Δk)	-0.10812 +/- 0.00001
Reactor Power (MW)	100
Maximum Propellant Exit Temperature (K)	3072
Specific Impulse (s)	372
Total Thrust (kN)	42

II.B. Propellant Management System

Most nuclear propulsion systems in the literature present a NERVA-like configuration²⁰, where the propellant passes through a reactor to absorb heat before expanding through a convergent-divergent nozzle; the propellant is stored at a pressure of about 5 bar inside the tanks and pressurized by inert gas and is sent into the reactor via a turbopump. The propellant management system, therefore, provides a pressure-fed configuration in which a gas different from the propellant pressurizes the tank containing the propellant in the liquid phase. This type of pressurization system is generally not suitable for reusable propulsion systems²¹. The use of a pressure-fed system in a reusable space-tug operating between the Earth and the Moon implies two ways to design the system:

1. If the pressurizing gas is present on the lunar surface and extractable, it is possible to refill the pressurizing gas tank every time the propellant tank is filled;
2. If the pressurizing gas is not present on the lunar surface or is difficult to extract, the system must be launched into orbit with a sufficient amount of pressurizing gas and complete the mission, considering multiple propellant refills.

Both solutions imply an increase in costs: the first one makes it necessary to mine Helium or other inert gases on the lunar surface, store it, and send the tanks into orbit together with the propellant tanks; this would lead to a doubling of costs, having to repeat the extraction, storing, and launch process for two substances. With the second, the mass to be inserted into NSO increases, and therefore, also in this case, the mission costs increase. The best solution to pressurize the propellant of a reusable vehicle is autogenous-pressurization²¹. In autogenous-pressurized propellant management systems, the propellant itself is left to evaporate and used as a pressurizer; this process allows the use of a single fluid on board and makes the option 1 seen for pressure-fed systems much more attractive since it is not necessary to mine, store and send into lunar orbit two fluids to make the system reusable, but only one. Autogenous pressurization allows for maximizing the

advantage provided by the NTP for reusable vehicles by making the entire propulsion system operate thanks to one single fluid. In a previous work²², we proposed a methodology for the sizing of a autogenous-pressurization system for the ammonia NTP; this system exploits the energy lost by the reactor in terms of radiation emitted towards the outside space by having it absorbed by a volume of ammonia in saturation conditions. The thermal input causes a vaporization of ammonia with a consequent increase in the tank pressure. The excess in pressure is used to pressurize the volume of liquid ammonia used as propellant to the desired level, thanks to a vapor flow between the pressurizing tank and the propellant tank regulated by a pressure regulator. Fig. 5 schematizes the process described. The developed methodology helped in designing this propellant management system for the proposed mission. The total volume for the propellant tank (RT) was set to approximately 35 m³ to contain the propellant necessary to perform all the maneuvers required to reach LLO. The determination of the volume of the pressurizing tank (PT) and the mass of saturated ammonia inside it was carried out through an iterative procedure. The procedure involved the insertion of a first guess of the shape and size of PT on OpenMC to estimate the thermal input reaching the tank; subsequently, a lumped-parameter thermo-hydraulic analysis determined the coupled dynamics of the volumes in the two tanks, verifying whether it was possible, with the PT guess, to maintain a constant pressure of 20 bar inside RT during both firings of the NSO-LLO journey. The procedure was repeated until the assumed PT volume was able to satisfy the imposed requirement; the requirement of a pressure of 20 bar in RT will reduce the probability of pump cavitation and recover the expected pressure loss in the coolant channels. The properties obtained for this propellant management system are reported in Table III. Fig. 6 shows the evolution of the pressure in the tanks estimated through the model described in the authors' previous work²². During the first firing in NSO, the heat input calculated with the OpenMC tally is 68322 W, while the mass flow rate exiting RT is 11.9 kg/s. After the first firing, the reactor is again made subcritical; a conservative value of the decay heat due to the gammas reaching the tank with an approximated law over time²³ allows for estimating the heat input during the coasting phase (about 3 days); during this phase, no mass flow exits RT. Once reached the LLO, the reactor is again operated at nominal power, providing the heat input of 68322 W at PT, and the mass flow exiting RT is again 11.9 kg/s. From the figure, it is possible to see how the system guarantees a feeding pressure of 20 bar during both firings. The system will refill the propellant and pressurant tanks in LLO and then restart its mission with multiple roundtrips between LLO and NRHO. The NSO-LLO trip was used to size the PMS since it is the one that provides the longest consecutive firing and, therefore, the largest pressure decrease in PT. The analysis can be repeated for the

roundtrip between LLO and NRHO, demonstrating that the volume obtained for PT is also sufficient for the propellant pressurization during this phase of the mission.

Table III. PMS Features

Parameter	Value
PT Ammonia Volume Heat Input	68322 W
PT Wall Heat Input	49758 W
RT Exiting Mass Flow Rate	11.9 kg/s
PT Volume	4.5 m ³
RT Volume	35 m ³
PT MEOP	70 bar
RT MEOP	30 bar
PT Material	Aluminum
RT Material	Ti6Al4V
PT and RT Shape	Cylindrical with Ellipsoidal Heads

Fig. 5. Propellant Management System with Autogenous Pressurization Schematic

Fig. 6. RT and PT Dynamics during the First Firing in NSO (top) and during the First Segment of the Mission (bottom)

II.C. Propulsion System Components Masses

Table IV shows the masses of the various components of the propulsion system and the payload available at NSO, confirming that an IMNSO of about 30000 metric tons is possible for the proposed space-tug. The Tsiolkovsky rocket equation with the imposed calculated masses determines the propellant mass needed during the various phases of the mission. Comparing the propellant mass needed for each roundtrip between LLO and NRHO with the RT capacity, it is possible to estimate that the system will have to reload the propellant after every two roundtrips.

Table IV. Propulsion System Mass Budget

Component	Mass (kg)
Shield	1300
Turbopump Assembly	30
Pressure Vessel	1000
Fission Reactor	3000
Propellant Management System (dry mass)	2400
Propellant (NH ₃)	20380
Pressurant (saturated NH ₃)	770
IMNSO	30000
Payload Mass Available @ NSO	1120

Table V. Maneuvers Timing and Propellant Consumption

	Δv (m/s)	Transfer Time (days)	Firing Time (s)	Propellant Mass (kg)
Trans.lunar injection	3288	3	1482.2	17713
Moon circ. (LLO)	900	0	222.9	2264
LLO- NRHO roundtrip	1404	0.5 0.5	586.3 295.8	10540

At this point, it is possible to determine whether the proposed system allows for obtaining a gain in terms of mass to be launched into Earth orbit compared to a system with pressure-fed PMS for a reusable space-tug operating in a cislunar environment.

III. PMS COMPARISON RESULTS

Assuming that the pressure-fed option’s propellant management system can also be refilled with propellant and assuming that empty pressurant bottles can be ejected from the system, it is possible to estimate the number of cycles (LLO-NRHO-LLO) that the propulsion system can complete with a single propellant refill, before the next refill. Considering that each pressurant bottle is used to pressurize an entire propellant load and that with the ejection of empty bottles, the propellant mass required to complete a cycle is reduced compared to that of the previous cycle, it is possible to evaluate whether with pressure-fed it is possible to perform more cycles before refilling the propellant compared to the number of cycles that can be performed with the autogenous-pressurization PMS. Taking a refilling range between 1 and 10, we can evaluate the mass of the propulsion system using pressure-fed after each refill and evaluate the propellant mass necessary to complete a cycle. What emerges is that the pressure-fed system needs refilling after 2-2.3 cycles, after 1-10 refillings respectively; in any case, since partial refillings would not be economically sustainable, the system needs to be refilled after two roundtrips: this is the same number of cycles expected before refilling the autogenous-pressurized configuration. Therefore, it is possible to associate both configurations with the same time scale for propellant refillings. At this point, the mass needed for a mission during 10 refilling can be estimated. The mass of the pressure-fed system depends on the number of refillings linearly, following Eq.(5), while the one of the autogenous-pressurized is independent from the number of refilling. Fig. 7 shows this comparison, while Fig. 8 shows the two analyzed configurations. The mass of the pressure-fed PMS was calculated considering a pressure of about 6 bar in the RT (as in the NERVA

configuration²⁰) and estimating the mass of the bottles and the pressurant starting from the mass of propellant to be pressurized and assuming an adiabatic expansion of the pressurant.

$$m_{pressure-fed} = m_{tank} + n(m_{bottle} + m_{gas}) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 7. Propellant Management System Masses vs. Number of Propellant Refilling Comparison

The result of this analysis shows that in terms of mass to be inserted into Earth orbit at the beginning of the mission and, therefore, in terms of costs, it is more convenient to use the proposed autogenous-pressurized PMS compared to a pressure-fed system only if the mission includes more than 4 propellant reloading cycles, i.e. more than 8 roundtrips between LLO and NSO. The factor limiting the number of performable roundtrips is the nuclear fuel burnup. A burnup analysis for the proposed reactor can highlight how long the reactor can perform the required mission, i.e. it can indicate the total number of cycles that can be achieved by the space-tug before the nuclear fuel is consumed; this number of cycles will indicate which one of the two systems is more convenient to use for the analyzed mission scenario.

Fig. 8. Pressure-fed (left) and Auto-pressurized (right) Propellant Management System Schematics

IV. REACTOR BURNUP ANALYSIS

The burnup analysis for the nuclear reactor was performed using OpenMC. Eight timesteps composed the analysis, following the transfer times and the firing times reported in the Table V; it is worth mentioning that the system will stay in LLO for about 7 days before firing to reach NRHO²⁴. The burnup analysis steps are the following:

- The first timestep includes the firing in NSO, and the reactor operates at full power.
- The second timestep includes the transit time between NSO and LLO with the reactor turned off
- The third timestep includes the fire to circularize the orbit at LLO with the reactor back at nominal power
- The fourth timestep includes the seven days that the system spends in LLO before starting the roundtrips; the reactor is turned off again
- The fifth, sixth, seventh, and eighth timesteps represent the system transitions from LLO to NRHO, with alternating ignition and coasting periods; these steps are repeated five times to simulate five propellant reloading cycles and verify if the reactor can operate for more than the four cycles (the identified threshold value).

Fig. 9 shows the results of the burnup analysis, highlighting how the nuclear fuel depletion for the selected configuration and mission scenario allows for completing at least five roundtrips between LLO and NRHO, making the PMS with autogenous pressurization the best solution for the proposed application.

Fig. 9. Nuclear Reactor Fuel Burnup Analysis Results

V. CONCLUSIONS

The work presented illustrates the preliminary sizing of a reusable nuclear thermal propulsion system for missions in cislunar environment. The system uses a HALEU particle bed reactor weighing 3000 kg and generating a power of 100 MW, suitable to provide a thrust of 42 kN using ammonia as propellant. Future phases of this work will focus on the reduction of the reactor mass and on the study of the ammonia decomposition process to

increase the specific impulse of the system and allow the insertion of a greater payload mass in the initial Earth orbit; at the moment, the IMNSO is 30000 kg and can be inserted into orbit with a single launch taking as payload a mass slightly above 1 t. However, the transportable mass between NSO and LLO is not the main feature of the system, but the great advantage provided by the proposed configuration is the complete reusability to perform multiple roundtrips between LLO and NRHO. The PMS implemented in the proposed solution uses an autogenous-pressurization principle to maintain the propellant inside the run tank at 20 bar for the duration of all the firings foreseen for the mission. The mass of the PMS that uses the radiation emitted by the reactor to pressurize the ammonia is about 2.4 metric tons; however, it gives great versatility to the propulsion system, making it dependent on a single fluid. Moreover, a comparison with a pressure-fed solution demonstrates how the designed NTP system can reduce the mass of the propulsion system to be launched into orbit at the beginning of the mission, reduce the costs for fluid refilling in lunar orbit, and complete multiple roundtrips between the LLO and the Lunar Gateway until it reaches complete consumption of the nuclear fuel; the system's mass reduction in Earth orbit increases with the number of roundtrips between LLO and NRHO going from 1 metric tons for 10 roundtrips to 4 metric tons for 20 roundtrips. The space-tug has been sized to transfer payload masses between 16 and 3 metric tons between the two stations and requires refilling of propellant and pressurizer, both consisting of ammonia, every 2 roundtrips, once returned to LLO. The refilling is made possible by the presence of ammonia in the lunar regolith that will be mined by the human outpost on the Moon. This study shows that an ammonia-fed HALEU NTP system using autogenous pressurization is a viable solution for cislunar missions; future efforts will focus on the detailed design of the components of this propulsion system to reduce component masses and increase performance to make it an even more competitive configuration.

NOMENCLATURE

ρ = density [kg/m³]

σ = material yield strength [MPa]

BOL= Beginning of Life

HALEU= High-Assay Low Enriched Uranium

HEO= High Earth Orbit

IMLEO= Initial Mass in Low Earth Orbit

IMNSO= Initial Mass in Nuclear Safe Orbit

ISRU= In-Situ Resource Utilization

LLO= Low Lunar Orbit

m_γ = mass of the gamma-absorbing shield layer [kg]

m_{bottle} = pressurant bottle mass [kg]

MEOP= Maximum Expected Operating Pressure

m_{gas} = pressurant mass [kg]

m_n = mass of the neutron-absorbing shield layer [kg]

$m_{pressure-fed}$ = pressure-fed PMS mass [kg]

m_{pv} = pressure vessel mass [kg]
 m_{tank} = propellant tank mass [kg]
 m_{tp} = Turbopump assembly mass [kg]
 n = number of propellant refilling
 NSO= Nuclear Safe Orbit
 NTP= Nuclear Thermal Propulsion
 NRHO= Near Rectilinear Halo Orbit
 p_c = reactor's feeding pressure [Pa]
 PMS= Propellant Management System
 PT= Pressurizing Tank
 P_{tp} = Turbine power [W]
 r = shadow shield layer radius [m]
 RT=Run Tank
 t = shadow shield layer thickness [m]
 TLI= Trans-Lunar Injection

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